

ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT AND INCOME INEQUALITY NEXUS IN NIGERIA: A NEW PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the nexus between financial development and income inequality in Nigeria, using quarterly time series data for various indicators of financial development. The indicators of financial development were separated into three namely banking sector development indicators, capital market indicators and the bond market development indicators respectively. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model with bounds testing was employed for analyzing the data used in this study. The result showed that financial development is a major driver of income inequality during the period of study; specifically, banking sector development and bond market development indicators of financial development significantly influenced income inequality in the long run while the capital market indicators insignificantly influenced income inequality. The study concludes that the effect of financial development on income inequality in Nigeria is sensitive to the indicator of financial development adopted and specifically, policymakers are encouraged to pay adequate attention to the workings of the financial market to ensure its activities are targeted towards providing a fair balance in the allocation to income and investment returns in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Financial Development, Income Inequality, Capital Market, Bond Market, Autoregressive Distributed Lag

JEL Codes: E61, E64, G21, G28, O11,

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1. INTRODUCTION

The objective of this paper is to examine the effect of financial development on income inequality in Nigeria, with the view to understand how the three main sections of financial development influenced income inequality during the period of study. Generally, income inequality refers to the concentration of income and wealth in the hands of a certain percentage or fraction of the citizens of a country and it encompasses all efforts of the government and the monetary authorities directed towards ensuring a balance in the allocation of income and wealth in the economy (Ogujiuba, Olamide & Olaniran, 2024; Kavya & Shijin, 2020; Jung & Cha, 2021; Ihemezie, 2025). The rising level of income inequality over time has spurred the adoption of various global measures aimed at tackling income inequality by several governments such as massive subsidy schemes, employment programs, progressive taxation and the decentralisation of public goods. Ibrahim & Okoh (2022) and Oxfam (2018) revealed that in Nigeria for instance, the annual earning of the richest Nigerian estimated at about \$24 million is enough to raise two million people out of poverty for a year.

The National Bureau of Statistics (hereafter, NBS) in 2017 reported that income inequality measured by the Gini coefficient worsened in Nigeria between 2004 and 2013 when its value rose from 0.356 to 0.41, but it experienced a slight improvement in 2016, when the value slightly fell to 0.391 (Davytan, 2017). More recently, income inequality reduced slightly between 2018 and 2024 with an average Gini coefficient value of 0.35 as a result of combative measures such as progressive taxation and social intervention programs targeted at improving the livelihood of the poor, though the effects of these policies are still far from achieving the global standard level of income inequality (NBS, 2024; Chletsos & Sintos, 2023; Dan'Asabe & Mustapha, 2023). As a result of the inequality experienced over time, the share of household's consumption in Nigeria revealed that the poorest households (bottom 10%) consumed 2.56% of products in the economy while the top 10% (the super-rich households) consumed 26.59% of all products in the economy. In the same vein, the top 20% were responsible for over 42% of the national income in Nigeria in 2004, about 49% in 2013 and around 49% in 2020 (NBS, 2021, Nadabo, et al., 2024).

Over the years, the role of financial development as a driver for long term macroeconomic performance has been extensively debated in the extant literature (O'Farrell, Rawdanowicz & Inaba, 2016; Aderajo & Olaniran, 2021; Neves & Silva, 2014, Olaniran & Aderajo, 2018; Zakari & Mohammed, 2025; Engle *et al.* 2013; Khatatbeh *et al.* 2022), but its influence on income inequality has received lesser attention over time. As pointed out in the studies of Galor & Zeira (1993), Classens & Perotti (2007) and more recently Younsi & Bechtini (2018) and Chisadza & Biyase (2023), income inequality is largely generated by the dynamics of financial development. The argument here is that if financial development stimulates access to financial services by low income earners in the economy, income inequality inevitably reduces. However, if financial sector activities cater basically for the rich due to credit restrictions, collateral requirements, creditworthiness etc., income inequality becomes more pronounced in the economy since poor households cannot meet up with such requirements (Daniel & Olaniran, 2017; Okafor et al., 2023, Bassey et al. 2025).

Economic theory provides divergent theoretical standpoint on the relationship between financial development and income inequality. A strand of early theorists such as Banerjee & Newmann,(1993) as well as Galor & Zeira (1993) argue that financial development negatively influences income inequality. This is because as a result of financial imperfections such as transaction cost, collateral requirements and information asymmetries', low income households find it difficult to access loans in the economy, thereby worsening income inequality in the economy. Another strand of theorists such as Greenwood & Jovanovic (1990), Shahbaz et al., (2015), Akintunde & Olaniran (2022) and Tita & Aziakpono (2016) argue that the financial development-income inequality nexus takes the form of an inverted U-shape hypothesis. This implies that at low levels of economic development, access to financial services is restricted to a few and hence raises income inequality, but as the economy develops, activities between the surplus and deficit units increases and access to financial services significantly increases, which in turn reduces income inequality in the economy.

In the empirical literature, there is no consensus on the precise nature of the relationship between financial development and income inequality. While some studies have established a positive relationship between financial development and income inequality (see Law & Tan, 2009; Jauch & Watzka, 2012; Fowowe & Abidoye, 2013; Younsi & Bechtini, 2018; Brei, Ferri & Gambacorta, 2018; Bolarinwa et al., 2021; Manta et al., 2023; De-Haan et al. 2018; Huynh & Tran, 2023), some others established a negative relationship between financial development and income inequality (Beck, Kunt & Levine, 2007; Kappel, 2010; Kim and Lin, 2011; Law, Tan & Saini, 2012; Dinler, 2015, Baiardi & Morana, 2018, Lee et al., 2022; Khatatbeh et al. 2022; Inoue, 2024; Huang et al. 2025). The implication of the foregoing is that the financial

development-income inequality debate is still largely ongoing and the variances in findings are possibly driven by the use of a single measure of financial development, the peculiar nature of different countries, frequency of data and the methodology adopted by these studies

Thus, this paper re-examines the financial development-income inequality nexus, and is a departure from previous studies in the following ways: Firstly, we divide financial sector development into three namely: banking sector development indicators, capital market development indicators and the bonds market development indicators respectively. To the best of our knowledge, no known study has examined the effect of each of these components on income inequality in Nigeria. Secondly, unlike previous studies that adopted a single measure of financial development, annual data or an index of financial development generated using Principal Component Analysis that is severely plagued by huge information loss in the data, this paper adopts quarterly time series data due to the volatile nature of the financial sector, as well as different measures of financial development, in order to strengthen the reliability of our estimation results. Finally, we estimate the effect of each of the aforementioned financial development segments on income inequality separately, in order to enhance the reliability of the result, since lumping different financial development indicators into a single model could lead to over-parametization issues, serial correlation and multicollinearity issues in the model.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: section two presents a brief literature review, section three contains the methodology while sections four and five contains the discussion of findings and the conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of previous studies on the financial development-income inequality nexus are discussed as follows. Kappel (2010) empirically investigated the effects of financial development on income inequality in seventy-eight (78) developing and developed countries for the period of 1960-2006. Using panel regression analysis of fixed effect (FE) and random effect (RE) estimation, the result showed that a well-developed financial sector reduces income inequality in the observed countries during the period of study. Similarly, Kim & Lin (2011) examined the linear and non-linear link between financial development and income inequality in a panel of sixty-five countries using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) and the Threshold regression methods of estimation. The findings revealed that financial development has a damaging influence on income inequality. The study of Nikoloski (2012) for selected advanced and developing countries using the dynamic multivariate panel data analysis provides strong empirical evidence that an inverted U-curve connection exists between the growth of financial sector and income inequality; thereby giving credence to the Greenwood & Jovanovic (1990) hypothesis. Kim & Lin (2023) examined the nexus between financial development, inflation and income inequality. In a sample consisting of 62 developed and developing countries between 1970 and 2019, the study revealed that Inflation raises income inequality and financial development moderates this adverse effect.

In a cross-country study by Johansson and Wang (2012) on the financial development-income inequality link in 66 advanced and developing countries using Instrumental Variable (IV) regression and the modeling average method. Findings revealed that credit restrictions and entry obstacles into the banking sector are the two most essential financial policies affecting income inequality. Also, Law, Tan & Saini (2014) using yearly data for 81 countries and the Instrumental Variable (IV) threshold regression technique, found that financial development decreases income inequality after a certain stage of institutional quality is achieved. They resolved that until a certain level of institutional quality is attained, there will be no connection between finance and income inequality. Denk & Cournède (2015) investigated the financial development-income inequality linkage for OECD nations using panel fixed effect (FE)

regression estimation technique. The result revealed that financial sector development increases income inequality in these countries. Also, the study found out evidence of reverse causality from greater income inequality to household borrowing in OECD nations in the period of study. In India, Sehrawat & Giri (2015) investigated financial development and income inequality using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bound co-integration technique. The findings of the study revealed that financial development further aggravates income inequality both in the short run and long run during the period of study. Beyond this, Daan et al. (2018) investigated the influence of financial development on income inequality in Asia, Africa and Latin America, by examining the role of financial liberalization in the nexus. The study found that the role of financial liberalization further strengthens the positive effect of the financial sector on income inequality.

In Africa, Fowowe & Abidoye (2013) adopted panel estimation GMM to probe the effect of financial development on inequality in Africa, whilst also incorporating the role of poverty in the framework. Findings revealed that financial development does not significantly impact poverty and inequality in Africa. Similarly, Mbutor & Uba (2013) by employing ordinary least square regression in Nigeria between 1980 to 2012, examined the empirical link between financial inclusion, inequality and monetary policy. The result revealed that growing financial inclusion will increase the efficacy and dependability of monetary policy and reduce income disparities in the economy. More recently, Okafor et al. (2023) examined the financial development and income inequality in Africa nexus using system generalized method moment and the results showed that access, stability and efficiency components of financial development reduce income inequality, while the depth dimension of financial development exacerbates income inequality in Africa. Altunbas & Thornton (2020) examined the impact of financial development on income inequality using quintile regression. The study found that the impact of financial development on income inequality changes with a country's income level such that equality is promoted across inequality quantiles in upper-middle income countries, and inequality is raised across inequality quantiles in low- and high-income countries.

Chletsos & Sintos (2023) researched the effect of financial development on income using 2127 estimates reported in 116 published studies that investigate the effect of financial development on income inequality. The study found that different measures of financial development and the inclusion of financial openness, inflation and income variables in the regressions matter significantly for the effect of financial development on inequality in the observed studies. Furthermore, Enemona et al. (2024) examined the nexus between Financial Development (FD) and Inclusive Growth (IG) in Africa using an inclusive growth index that combined a number of macroeconomic variables in 27 African countries. The results showed that all financial development indicators exhibited only a significant impact on the inclusive growth index in the long run with mixed nexus reported in the short run. Similarly, Inoue (2024) examined the influence of financial inclusion on income distribution using panel data between 2004 and 2021. The findings revealed that financial inclusion have significant negative effects on income inequality; and that such effects vary depending on the dimension of financial inclusion adopted.

In Nigeria, Yinusa & Alimi (2015) tested the Greenwood and Jovanovic (GJ) hypothesis using annual time series data adopted the Johannssen cointegration test and the error correction technique of analysis. The study found out that financial development increases income inequality during the period of study, thereby refuting the Greenwood and Jovanovic (GJ) hypothesis in Nigeria. Ayinde & Yinusa (2016) examined the nexus between financial development and inclusive growth by using income inequality as one of the measures of inclusive growth in Nigeria as well as the direction of causality between them. The

methodology adopted is quantile regression and the study found out that the effect of financial development on income inequality, and other measures of inclusive growth depends on the indicator of financial development adopted. The study also found out that the direction of causality runs from inclusive growth to financial development in Nigeria. Isah & Hamzat (2017) used financial depth, financial efficiency, financial stability and financial liberalization as measures of financial development and both net and gross Gini coefficient as measures of income inequality. By employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique, the study found that financial development positively drives income inequality in Nigeria except for financial liberalization. Beyond this, Nadabo et al. (2024) examined the effect of financial development on income inequality using the ARDL bounds testing and the Toda-Yammamoto technique of estimation. The study found evidence of the existence of the inverted U-shaped hypothesis in Nigeria, as well as a unidirectional causal relationship running from financial development to income inequality.

In a different study, Sehrawat & Giri (2016) explored the nexus between financial development and rural-urban income inequality in six South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) countries, while considering the role of economic growth. By employing panel fully modified ordinary least square (FMOLS) regression analysis, the study found out that improvements in the financial system and economic growth heighten rural-urban income inequality during the period of study. Isah & Soliu (2016) also carried out a detailed review of the previous studies as regards the connection of financial development to income inequality in advanced, emerging and unindustrialized nations. The methodology adopted is a systematic review of abstracts, conclusions and the paper as a whole in some cases. The findings revealed that a substantial amount of existing studies found an inverse link between financial development and income inequality, with most of these studies confirming the Greenwood & Jovanovic (1990) hypothesis. Younsi & Bechtini (2018) for Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa (BRICS) examined output, financial development and income inequality between 1995 and 2015 and the study found a positive link between GDP per capita growth and income inequality, but the nonlinear coefficient revealed an inverse but significant impact on inequality. Baiardi & Morana (2018) observed financial development-income inequality tie in the Euro area using annual data observations between 1985 and 2013, the GMM technique as well as counterfactual analysis. The study found robust support for an Euro area-wide Kuznets curve and for continuous convergence amidst EA members. Also, the study further revealed that income inequality worsened in the entire Euro area. Rahman, Fuquan & Ara (2019) examined non-linear dynamics in the finance-inequality link and tested the Greenwood & Jovanovic hypothesis. The study used data for China Health and Nutrition Survey (CHNS) and adopted the Quantile Regression (QR) model to analyze the data collected. The result revealed that financial development has a direct but asymmetric influence on the yearly incomes of persons from different income grades at varying quartiles. Also, the study supported the Greenwood & Jovanovic hypothesis.

3. METHODOLOGY

To examine the effect of financial development on income inequality in Nigeria, the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model proposed by Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001) is adopted. This is because the ARDL approach also incorporates the short-run dynamics since relying upon the long-run dynamics will not be adequate (Daniel & Olaniran, 2017; Alimi & Olaniran, 2019). Also, ARDL can be applied on time series data regardless of the level of stationarity of the variables. After the unit root test, bound test for cointegration is used to test whether the variables are co-integrated to ascertain long run relationship.

The baseline model for examining the relationship between financial development and income inequality in Nigeria is specified in functional form as follows:

$$Y_t = f(\text{FD}_t, \text{EXR}_t) \tag{1}$$

Where FD is financial development which is broken down into three (3) based on various indicators of financial development in the empirical literature. The first is the banking sector development indicators (bsd) that comprises of financial depth indicators of financial development which includes the ratio of broad money supply to gross domestic product (M2/GDP) and the ratio of private sector credit to gross domestic product (CPS/GDP). The second is capital market development indicator which comprises of financial deepening indicators of financial development which includes ratio of stock market capitalization to gross domestic product and the ratio of the value of stocks traded to gross domestic product, as well as financial liberalization (measured by the Chinn-Ito index). The third is the financial innovation indicator of financial development which is the ratio of debt stock to gross domestic product in Nigeria. Beyond this, Y_t is income inequality denoted by the Gini coefficient, while EXR_t is exchange rate which serves as the control variable for model robustness.

Re-writing equation (1) in an explicit and econometric form gives:

$$\text{INQ}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{BSD}_t + \beta_2 \text{CMD}_t + \beta_3 \text{BMD}_t + \beta_4 \text{EXR}_t + e_t \tag{2}$$

Based on the specification in equation 2, an ARDL model is constructed to reflect both the short run equilibrium and the long run dynamics as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \text{inq}_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \mu_i \Delta \text{inq}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{\rho} \delta_i \Delta \text{bsd}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{\rho} \phi_i \Delta \text{cmd}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{\rho} \sigma_i \Delta \text{bmd}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{\rho} \theta_i \Delta \text{exr}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{\rho} \lambda_i \Delta u_{t-i} + \gamma_1 \text{inq}_{t-1} \\ & + \gamma_2 \text{bsd}_{t-1} + \gamma_3 \text{cmd}_{t-1} + \gamma_4 \text{bmd}_{t-1} + \gamma_5 \text{exr}_{t-1} + \gamma_6 u_{t-1} + e_t \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Equation (3) denotes the unrestricted version of ARDL specification which models the link between financial development and income inequality where Δ is the difference operator, α the drift component, e_t is white noise, γ are the long run multipliers. It is pertinent to note that three separate models are estimated for each of the groups of financial development indicators used in this study to prevent spurious result and enhance the reliability of the findings. This is done to prevent issues such as serial correlation, multicollinearity and endogeneity issues that may arise from lumping all the indicators of financial development into a single model.

Data used in this study were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and the Standardized World Income Inequality Index (SWIID) and the dataset used is available on request.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Unit Root and Correlation Matrix

In time series analysis, examining the descriptive properties of the variables is pertinent and in tandem with standard practice. This is because it helps to understand the distribution and variability of the dataset, and it provides us with information about the symmetry, skewness, peakness, maximum and minimum values; as well as the standard deviation of the observed variables. The result of the descriptive analysis in table 1 reveals that the mean and median values are quite close to each other and falls within the maximum and minimum values, depicting a good level of symmetry, consistency and normal distribution for these variables. It is also observed that the ratio of broad money supply to the gross domestic product had the highest standard deviation value, thereby indicating it fluctuated the most among the variables, while financial liberalization exhibited the lowest fluctuations, as it had the lowest value for standard deviation. In terms of skewness, two of the variables namely income inequality and financial liberalization are negatively skewed while the other variables are positively skewed

and the kurtosis statistics revealed that the variables are leptokurtic since five of the variables had a value that exceeded three. Beyond this, the Jarque Berra statistics for five of the variables falls below 5% significance level, thereby indicating randomness and normal distribution for the variables.

In terms of the correlation matrix, by taking income inequality as the dependent variable, it is observed that all the variables are negatively correlated with income inequality except for financial liberalization. As regards the degree of association among the variables, it is observed that a weak degree of association exist between the explanatory variables and the dependent variable.

Table 1:

Descriptive Statistics

	GINI	M2GDP	CPSGDP	MKTCAPGDP	SVT_GDP	DBTSTCK	FINLIB
Mean	38.38269	14.18672	11.74292	10.76031	1.25255	5.751943	-1.2296
Median	38.60938	4.347367	2.904078	0.706244	0.11377	1.669253	-0.8732
Maximum	42.40313	80.74251	78.64405	92.94427	11.9829	33.45977	-0.5838
Minimum	35.52708	0.406409	0.229915	0.074446	-0.6102	0.043071	-2.6679
Std. Dev.	1.605256	20.05773	19.07509	18.95947	2.47813	8.136565	0.63906
Skewness	0.210265	1.70129	1.950279	2.219786	2.43094	1.682905	-0.5128
Kurtosis	2.505668	4.544345	5.43799	7.857402	8.69405	4.779832	1.75381
Jarque-Bera	2.2991	76.21225	115.4882	236.3685	305.995	79.12661	14.2186
Probability	0.316779	0	0	0	0	0	0.00082
Sum	5028.132	1858.461	1538.322	1409.6	164.438	753.5046	-161.07
Sum Sq. Dev.	334.99	52300.62	47323.56	46729.98	798.343	8606.67	53.1822
Observations	131	131	131	131	131	131	131

Correlation Matrix

	GINIUPD	M2GDPPUPD	CPS_GDP	MKTCAPGDP	SVT_GDP	DBTSTCK	FINLIB_OP
GINI	1	-0.1511738	0.1756944	-0.0619334	-0.1556	-0.1248245	0.19644
M2GDP	0.1511738	1	0.9867883	0.8203001	0.83121	0.982715	0.50664
CPSGDP	0.1756944	0.9867883	1	0.7655506	0.80763	0.9746662	0.47272
MKTCAPGDP	0.0619334	0.8203001	0.7655506	1	0.90951	0.8087422	0.49793
SVTGDP	0.1556146	0.8312066	0.8076316	0.9095127	1	0.8093562	0.4344
DBTSTCK	0.1248245	0.982715	0.9746662	0.8087422	0.80936	1	0.53271
FINLIB	0.1964431	0.5066446	0.4727176	0.497928	0.4344	0.5327064	1

4.2 Graphical Analysis of Financial Development and Income Inequality

To provide a stronger argument for the relationship between financial development and income inequality in Nigeria in this study, it is imperative to carry out a graphical analysis to better understand the relationship between them. From figure 1, financial development indicators fluctuated slightly in an increasing manner between 1986 and 2004 while income inequality remained relatively stable between these periods. The reason for this is attributed to the introduction of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986 to provide economic stabilization and reduce income inequality and the payment systems modernization policy that led to the introduction and wide usage of electronic payment systems between 2001 and 2004.

Also, the bank recapitalization and consolidation policy introduced in 2004; amongst other things strengthened the financial sector by providing stronger capital base for banks through mergers and acquisitions, as well as the absorption of weaker banks by the stronger banks; thereby improving financial stability and the gains of monetary policy.

However, the period between 2006 and 2014 brought about severe fluctuations in financial development between due to the instability in the monetary policy rate, increased debt profile, the proposed re-denomination of the naira which was later halted, the effect of the global financial crisis (GFC) of 2008 and its attendant effect in the subsequent years. All these led to severe financial shocks and spurred recovery efforts by the Nigerian government which is also the case in global parlance, thereby leading to a slight reduction in income inequality in these periods. In the subsequent periods, financial development indicators remained increasingly stable as a result of financial stabilization policies such as monetary policy tightening, foreign exchange reforms, conditional cash transfers and more recently the bank recapitalization policy put in place amongst several other things; while income inequality rose between the first quarter of 2014 and the last quarter of 2017 but fell and remained stable in the subsequent periods. The foregoing provides evidence that income inequality is largely affected by the performance of the financial sector in Nigeria.

Figure 1: Graph of Financial Development indicators and Income Inequality in Nigeria 100

4.3 Analysis of the Unit Root Test

In an attempt to test for the stationarity of the variables, this study employed both the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillip-Peron (PP) test with constant term. The results of the ADF and the PP tests are as shown in table 2. Based on the result of the unit root test presented in table 2, both the Augmented Dickey Fuller and the Phillip Peron tests indicates that all the variables are stationary at their first difference (I1) except for income inequality (Gini) that is stationary in its level form i.e. I(0). This means the variables are a combination of I(1) and I(0) which then supports the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) framework in examining the effect of financial development on income inequality in Nigeria during the period of study.

Table 2: Unit Root Test

Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test				Phillip-Peron (PP) Test		
Variables	Level	1st Difference	Status	Level	1st Difference	Status
GINI	-3.8877 (0.0153)**	- -	I(0)	-3.8116 (0.0159)**	- -	I(0)
M2/GDP	-1.7527 -0.7219	-11.8053 (0.0000)**	I(1)	-1.7076 -0.7426	-11.8504 (0.0000)**	I(1)
CPS/GDP	-1.7295 -0.7327	-10.4635 (0.0000)**	I(1)	-1.8505 -0.6743	-10.4681 (0.0000)**	I(1)
MKTCAP/GDP	-2.3769 -0.3998	-9.3846 (0.0000)**	I(1)	-2.209 -0.4803	-9.2842 (0.0000)**	I(1)
SVT/GDP	-2.5519 -0.3031	-10.7413 (0.0000)**	I(1)	-2.8005 -0.1999	-11.1173 (0.0000)**	I(1)
FINLIB	-1.5237 -0.8166	-5.6224 (0.0000)**	I(1)	-1.3028 -0.8829	-10.9245 (0.0000)**	I(1)
DEBTSTOCK/GDP	-1.6693 -0.7594	-10.9211 (0.0000)**	I(1)	-1.7464 -0.7249	-10.9245 (0.0000)**	I(1)
EXR	-1.5559	-10.2457	I(1)	-1.693	-10.1926	I(1)
	-0.0859	(0.0000)**		-0.7491	(0.0000)**	

Source: Author’s Computation

Note: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively. Critical values of the ADF and PP tests at 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance are -4.0325, -3.4459 and -3.1479 respectively.

4.4 Bounds Test Co-Integration Result

The long run relationship among the variables is tested with the null hypothesis of the non-existence of a long run relationship. The Pesaran et al. (2001) F-table is compared with the calculated F-statistics at various critical levels. From Table 3, the calculated F-statistics value is 9.6016 and it exceeds the upper bounds critical value of the Pesaran et al. (2001) bounds testing table. This implies that we reject the null hypothesis of no co-integration and accept the alternative hypothesis that says co-integration exists. Thus, long run relationship exists among the variable.

Table 3: Null Hyp: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistics	Value	K
F-Statistics	9.601674	7
Critical Bounds		
Significance	I(0)	I(1)
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
1%	3.74	5.06

Source: Author’s Computation

4.5 Effect of Banking Sector Development Indicators on Income Inequality in Nigeria.

A) SHORT RUN ANALYSIS

Table 4 presents the result of the short run effect of financial development (banking sector development indicators) on income inequality in Nigeria. It is observed that the ratio of broad money supply to GDP has a positive but insignificant effect on income inequality in Nigeria. Theoretically, this could be as a result of the inflation generated during monetary expansion in the economy, which erodes the value of money and eliminates its ability to reduce income inequality in Nigeria, since the monetarists strongly opine that inflation is strictly a monetary

phenomenon. This finding supports the view of Azleen & Mansur (2017) and Younsi & Bechtini (2018) for developing countries. In developed countries, this finding supports the views of Jauch & Watzka (2016), Baiardi & Morana (2018) as well as Isah & Hamzat (2017). In the case of the ratio of private sector credit to GDP, it is observed that credit to the private sector had a negative and significant effect on income inequality in Nigeria, at 5% significance level during the period of study. This means that the ratio of private sector credit to GDP worsens income inequality in Nigeria. The reason for this may be due to the fact that part of the funds made available to entrepreneurs and other private borrowers in the economy are not productively used in improving their standard of living; and policy makers must begin to put in place monitoring modalities to ensure appropriate and productive use of these funds. This could arise from spending the funds on unproductive activities like parties, acquisition of automobiles or other forms of unproductive ventures, instead of investing the funds in the real sector of the economy. Another reason which is pertinent to policy makers is that a large part of the funds channeled by banks to the private sector are not accessible to all classes of people due to a number of factors such as the interest rate charged (since monetary tightening comes with high interest rates), collateral restrictions, credit rating assessment as well as the other conditions attached to accessing the loan. This provides a reasonable explanation for the incessant shutdown of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs), high level of poverty and low standard of living bedeviling the Nigerian economy, and policy makers must begin to think of rational ways to tackle these restrictions to improve access to these funds by the poor. This finding supports the views of Sehrawat & Giri (2016) and Yinusa & Alimi (2015) for developing countries; and Kim & Lin (2011), Denk & Cournede (2015), Dinler (2015), as well as Inoue (2024) for developed countries.

For exchange rate that was introduced into the model as a control variable to strengthen the reliability of the model and prevent spurious result, it is observed that exchange rate in the current period as well as in the previous two periods, had a positive and significant effect on income inequality in Nigeria, that is, exchange rate reduced income inequality in these periods and this is in consonance with the theoretical expectation between them. By examining the speed of adjustment towards long run equilibrium, the adjustment or error correction term has a value of -0.085, and it is statistically significant at 5% significance level. This means that about 8.5% of the errors committed in the short run is corrected in the long run in Nigeria.

Table 4: Short Run Estimates
Dependent Variable: GINI
ARDL: 2, 0, 0, 3

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T. Stat	Prob.
D(GINI(-1))	0.619004**	0.084088	7.361418	0.0002
D(GINI(-2))	0.293441**	0.082114	3.573585	0.0005
D(MS/GDP)	0.006526	0.004698	1.389125	0.1675
D(CPS/GDP)	-0.011366**	0.004845	-2.34575	0.0207
D(EXR)	0.005175**	0.00158	3.28337	0.0014
D(EXR(-1))	-0.011465**	0.00224	-5.1138	0.0001
D(EXR(-2))	0.01767**	0.00245	7.2088	0.0002
D(EXR(-3))	-0.00328	0.00203	-1.6157	0.1089
CointEq(-1)	-0.085474**	0.0169	-5.0571	0.0001

Source: Author's Computation. Note: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively.

B) LONG RUN ANALYSIS

Table 5 presents the result of the long run relationship between financial and income inequality (GINI) in Nigeria. The result revealed that the ratio of broad money supply to GDP had a positive and significant effect on income inequality in Nigeria, unlike in the short run when its effect was insignificant. In other words, financial development reduces income inequality in Nigeria in the long run, during the period of study. The implication of this to policy makers is that if the reserve requirement of banks is low, their capacity to influence the financial sector increases through the provision of financial services to different groups and classes of people in the economy. This in turn increases people's access to funds and financial services (for productive activities) in the economy, which improves their standard of living and depresses income inequality in the process. This result supports the findings of Younsi and Bechtini (2018), Baiardi and Morana (2018), De-Haan et al. (2018) and Huynh & Tran (2023) in developed countries.

In the case of the ratio of private sector credit to GDP, the result showed that the ratio of private sector credit to GDP has a negative and significant effect on income inequality in Nigeria at 5% significance level. This supports the findings of the short run for private sector credit. This means that increasing the availability of credit to the private sector further widens the gap between the rich and the poor in the economy because the larger chunk of these credits are not made available to all classes of people in the economy, since the poor do not have collaterals and the credit rating to access such funds in most cases. For exchange rate, the effect is negative and significant indicating that it worsens income inequality in the economy in this model. This finding supports the view of previous studies such as Denk & Cournede (2015), Dinler (2015), Isah & Soliu (2016), Sehrawat & Giri (2016) and Inoue (2024).

Table 5: Long Run Estimates
Dependent Variable: GINI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T. Stat.	Prob
MS/GDP	0.137949**	0.059633	2.313284	0.0225
CPS/GDP	-0.132979**	0.058102	-2.2887	0.0239
EXR	-0.014283**	0.003967	-3.60068	0.0005
C	38.901206**	0.512641	75.88397	0.0001

Source: Author's Compilation

Note: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively.

4.6 Effect of Capital Market Development Indicators on Income Inequality in Nigeria.

A) Short Run Analysis

Table 6 presents the short run estimates of the dependent and independent variables. It is observed that market capitalization to GDP ratio in the short run has a positive but insignificant effect on income inequality in Nigeria during the period of study. Financial liberalization in the short run has a positive but insignificant effect on income inequality in the current period, but was positive and significant in the previous lag at 10% significance level. In the same vein, the ratio of the value of stocks traded to GDP in the short run, negatively but insignificantly affected income inequality in Nigeria during the period of study. However, exchange rate which is a control variable in Nigeria had a significant positive effect on income inequality indicating that exchange rate reduces income inequality in the short run. Thus, we can say that in the short run, all capital market indices do not significantly influence income inequality in Nigeria. Finally, the error correction term which examines the speed of adjustment towards long run equilibrium, is correctly signed and statistically significant and it revealed that about 11% of the errors committed in the short run are corrected in the long run in Nigeria.

Dependent Variable: GINI**Table 6: Short Run Estimates. ARDL: 3, 0, 1, 0 2**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T. Stat	Prob
D(GINI(-1))	0.507195	0.067956	7.463553	0.0000
D(GINI(-2))	0.294147	0.082351	3.57189	0.0005
D(GINI(-3))	0.144777	0.080839	1.790936	0.076
D(MKTCAP/GDP)	0.001585	0.001885	0.840743	0.4023
D(FINLIB)	0.052055	0.167722	0.310364	0.7569
D(FINLIB(-1))	0.300275	0.178808	1.679314	0.0959
D(SVT/GDP)	-0.016195	0.018724	-0.864935	0.3889
D(EXR)	0.005332	0.001597	3.339376	0.0011
D(EXR(-1))	-0.010674	0.002268	-4.706082	0.0001
D(EXR(-2))	0.014821**	0.001594	9.298451	0.0000
CointEq(-1)	-0.108724**	0.019021	-5.715945	0.0000

Source: Author's Computation.

Note: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively.

B) Long Run Analysis

Table 6 presents the long run estimates of the model. It is observed that in the long run, market capitalization to GDP ratio in Nigeria had a positive but insignificant effect on income inequality in Nigeria at 5% significance level. Also, the ratio of the value of stocks traded to GDP during the period of study was also positive but insignificant at 5% level of significance in Nigeria. This result support the findings of the short run and it basically reinforces the fact that the capital market does not play a major role in worsening income inequality in Nigeria and this is a pointer to policymakers to focus more on the workings of the money market in Nigeria to ensure the stability of short-term securities and investments to reduce income inequality in Nigeria. However, financial liberalization which measures the degree of economic and financial openness to the rest of the world negatively and significantly affected income inequality in Nigeria at 5% level of significance. The plausible reason for this could be attributed to the fact that the Nigerian financial sector is not well developed when compared to the financial sectors of advanced economies, thereby making it vulnerable and susceptible to global financial shocks, imported inflation and negative stock market spillovers from the rest of the world. For exchange rate, its effect on income inequality is significantly negative thereby indicating that it worsens income inequality in Nigeria, and this is in contrast with the findings of the short run. This is probably driven by the fact that the monetary authorities tend to influence and manage the value of the domestic currency in the short run, through the fixed or managed floating exchange rate system to achieve some level of economic and price stability. However in the long run, the exchange rate is largely liberalized and fully floated such that it is determined by the market forces of demand and supply, which could then reflect its true effect on macroeconomic variables and income inequality in Nigeria. The result supports the findings of Fowowe and Abidoye (2013), Tita and Aziakpono (2016) and Rahmani, Fuquan & Ara (2019).

Dependent Variable: GINI**Table 6: Long Run Estimates**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T. Stat	Prob
MKTCAP/GDP	0.014578	0.017013	0.856874	0.3933
FINLIB	-0.986744**	0.428839	-2.300964	0.0232
SVT/GDP	0.044586	0.133775	0.333288	0.7395
EXR	-0.010156**	0.003581	-2.836131	0.0050
C	38.002484	0.727356	52.247442	0.0001

Source: Author's Compilation

Note: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively.

4.7 Effect of Bond Market Development Indicator on Income Inequality in Nigeria.**A) Short Run Analysis**

Table 7 presents the short run result between the dependent and independent variables. It is observed that in the short run, debt stock to GDP ratio in Nigeria negatively and significantly influences income inequality. Debt stock refers to the total amount of debt a country owes to its creditors internally and externally. This means that debt stock (domestic and external) in Nigeria further widens (worsens) income inequality in Nigeria. By implication, as the country acquires more debt domestically and externally, income inequality becomes more pronounced in the economy. The reason for this could be that the debts acquired in Nigeria over time, have not been properly utilized and productively channeled, such that some people may have enriched their personal pockets, instead of using the debts to benefit the entire population.

The implication of this to policy makers is that adequate attention must be given to the rising debt profile in the country because the excessive and irresponsible acquisition of domestic and external debts has weakened the country's external reserves, slowed down the pace of growth and redistributed income inappropriately, due to corruption, nepotism and the weak structure of the monetary authorities in Nigeria. This finding is backed theoretically by the Keynesians who opined that a high debt stock makes a country subservient to the creditors, thereby weakening the country's currency and its current account position, which in turn drives down the value of money. The error correction term that denotes the speed of adjustment towards stability in the long run revealed that about 7.4% of the errors committed in the short run were corrected in the long run

Table 7: Short Run Estimates**Dependent Variable Gini; ARDL (2, 0, 3,)**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T. Stat	Prob
D(GINI(-1))	0.647944**	0.084121	7.702553	0.0000
D(GINI(-2))	0.281581**	0.083051	3.39047	0.0001
D(DEBTSTOCK/GDP)	-0.010284**	0.005665	-1.815208	0.0421
D(EXR)	0.004909**	0.001594	3.079025	0.0026
D(EXR(-1))	-0.011329**	0.002271	-4.987815	0.0000
D(EXR(-2))	0.018125**	0.002475	7.321841	0.0000
D(EXR(-3))	-0.004206**	0.002015	-2.086937	0.0391
CointEq(-1)	-0.074987**	0.017489	-4.287599	0.0000

Source: Author’s Computation. Note: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively.

B) Long Run Estimates

Table 8 presents the long run relationship between the dependent and independent variables. It is observed that in the long run, debt stock to GDP ratio in Nigeria has a positive and insignificant influence on income inequality at 5% significance level, during the period of study. Exchange rate fluctuations in the long run negatively and significantly affects income inequality in Nigeria, which means that exchange rate increases and worsens income inequality during the period of study.

Table 8: Long Run Estimates

Dependent Variable: Gini

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T. Stat	Prob
DEBTSTOCK/GDP	0.03022	0.03676	0.82215	0.4127
EXR	-0.015509**	0.00486	-3.1886	0.0018
C	39.320799**	0.57246	68.6875	0

Source: Author’s Computation

Note: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively.

4.8 DIAGNOSTIC TESTS

(I) Testing for Serial Correlation

According to the Breusch-Pagan test for serial correlation, the null hypothesis of no serial correlation is tested against the alternative hypothesis of serial correlation. In order to verify the existence of serial correlation in the model, the observed R-squared (Obs*R-squared) and its corresponding probability value (Pro. Chi-squared) is observed. In Table 9, the Obs*R-squared has a value 1.809842, while its corresponding p-value has a value of 0.0758. Since the probability value is greater than 5%, we accept the null hypothesis that there is no evidence of serial correlation in the model.

(II) The Test for Heteroscedasticity

To test for the presence of homoscedasticity in the model, the study chooses the Arch Test. In the Arch test, the Observed R-squared value is checked with its corresponding probability value. The null hypothesis here is that the model is homoscedastic, while the alternative hypothesis here is that the model is heteroscedastic. We reject the null hypothesis if this probability value is less than 5%. From Table 9, since the probability value of 0.0747 is greater than 0.05, at the 5% significance level, we accept the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity and reject the alternative hypothesis of presence of heteroscedasticity. Hence, the model is homoscedastic and this means the model has goodness of fit and the results are desirable.

Table 9: Serial Correlation and Heteroscedasticity Test Using the Breusch-Pagan and ARCH Method

	Serial Correlation	Heteroscedasticity
F-Statistics	0.817504	3.206323
Obs*R-Squared	1.809842	3.176154
Prob	0.4441	0.0758
Prob. Chi-Square	0.4046	0.0747

Source: Author’s Computation

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effect of financial development on income inequality using various proxies of financial development which are the banking sector development (bsd), capital market development (cmd) and bond market development (bmd) indicators of financial development. The study examined each of these variants of financial development in separate models for model estimation reliability. Prior to this, the graphical analysis carried out revealed that financial development fluctuated sharply throughout the period of study why income inequality remained quite stable. Beyond this, the unit root test carried out revealed that the variables are a mix of I(1) and I(0) and the correlation matrix revealed that most of the variables are negatively and weakly correlated with income inequality thereby indicating that the model estimated afterwards is reliable. The findings revealed that for bsd indicators, M2/GDP ratio insignificantly affected income inequality in Nigeria while CPS/GDP ratio negatively and significantly influenced income inequality in Nigeria both in the short and long run. For cmd indicators, MKTCAP/GDP and SVT/GDP ratio affected income inequality insignificantly both in the short and long run except for financial liberalization that was negative and significant in the long run. In the case of bmd indicators, DEBTSTOCK/GDP ratio significantly influenced income inequality only in the short run during the period of study.

The study concludes that the effect of financial development on income inequality is sensitive to the indicator of financial development employed and the effect of exchange rate as a (control variable) on income inequality varied based on the three models estimated in this study. Thus, policymakers are encouraged to pay adequate attention to the workings of the financial market to ensure its activities are targeted towards providing a fair balance in the allocation to income and investment returns in Nigeria.

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